

Queensland Plateau and Coral Sea Basin: Stratigraphy, Structure and Tectonics

by Lloyd Taylor and David Falvey
Department of Geology & Geophysics,
University of Sydney, Marine Studies
Contribution No. G50.

ABSTRACT

Seafloor spreading in the Coral Sea Basin is dated by Deep Sea Drilling Project Site 287 as Early Eocene (51 my bp). This requires normal rifting and breakup of an extended Australian continent including the Queensland, Papuan and Louisiade Plateaus as well as the Cretaceous portions of East Papua. A reconstruction based on continental and plateau margin physiography and Papua-New Guinea geology points to a pole of relative opening at lat. 11.3° S., long. 141.3° E. This results in left-lateral transform motion along the Moresby Trough and Bismarck-Lagaip Fault Zones through breakup, plus the deformation of the Owen Stanley sediment pile, and emplacement of the Papuan Ultramafic Belt.

Following initiation of sea-floor spreading, subsidence commenced at what are now the marginal plateaus bordering the Coral Sea Basin. A widespread unconformity spanning the late Eocene-mid Oligocene can be recognised on all plateaus as well as in the basin proper. This is attributed to the commencement of a significant equatorial circulation pattern in the deepening basin and over the subsided plateaus. Stabilisation of this equatorial circulation pattern permitted coral reef development on residual basement highs on the marginal plateaus and eventually on the subsiding Queensland continental shelf and Papuan stable platform areas in the late Oligocene-early Miocene.

On the basis of seismic refraction and gravity evidence, rift valley sequences up to 3 km thick are inferred beneath the Queensland and Townsville Troughs and bordering the Queensland and Papuan Plateaus. Though seismic refraction data are lacking, similar sequences are also inferred beneath parts of the Eastern and Marion Plateaus, Bligh Trough and Louisiade Rise. The age of this pre-breakup rifting is suggested to be mid Cretaceous-Palaeocene although direct evidence is absent.

Gravity modelling over the Queensland Trough, Plateau and Coral Sea Basin supports the interpretation from seismic reflection and refraction data. Continental crustal structure with a deep metamorphic layer is indicated for the Queensland Trough and Plateau with a depth to the Moho of 22-28 km. The continental/oceanic crust transition occurs towards the base of the continental slope at a water depth of up to 4.5 km along the Queensland Plateau. Crust beneath the Coral Sea abyssal plain is oceanic with a depth to mantle of 11-13 km.

INTRODUCTION

The Western Coral Sea lies within the Melanesian arc and separates south-east Papua New Guinea from Australia. The region consists of an abyssal plain at 4500 metres depth bordered by continental marginal plateaus (Fig. 1). Normal

Fig. 1. Western Coral Sea location map. Bathymetric contours are at 500 m intervals (after Taylor, 1977). Seismic stations (M. Ewing et al., 1970; and J. Ewing et al., 1970) and Deep Sea Drilling Project Sites are indicated. Projected gravity profiles AA' and BB' are Figure 9 and 10 respectively. The heavy contour lines show the geoidal gravity anomaly (Kaula, 1972).

heat flow, deeply subsided oceanic basement and the absence of seismicity (Sclater, 1972; Sclater & Ritter, 1972; Macdonald et al., 1973; Halunen & Von Herzen, 1973; Barazangi & Dorman, 1969) characterise it as an inactive oceanic basin. Karig (1971) classified it as an inactive marginal basin though we consider it to be the result of normal sea-floor spreading and not of island arc migration as envisaged by Karig.

Legs 21 and 30 of the Deep Sea Drilling Project (D.S.D.P.) have confirmed that the basin is inactive. The stratigraphy of Sites 209 and 210 is described comprehensively in Burns, Andrews et al. (1973) and that of Site 287 in Andrews, Packham et al. (1975). Site 209 on the eastern margin of the Queensland Plateau cored a Middle Eocene-Recent section and together with Sites 210 and 287 on the Coral Sea Abyssal

Fig. 2. Generalised time-stratigraphic cross-section from the Queensland Shelf to the Coral Sea Basin. The onset and cessation of seafloor spreading in the Coral Sea Basin is assumed to have been approximately 55 and 50 m.yrs. respectively, but these times are constrained only by DSDP Site 287. East Papua New Guinea and the Papuan Plateau was translated to the right by roughly 200 km by this seafloor spreading episode. Situations analogous to DSDP Sites 209, 210 and 287 are shown (modified after Falvey and Taylor, 1974).

Plain established the presence of a late Eocene-middle Oligocene submarine unconformity in the region. Site 287 located on a basement high northeast of the centre of the abyssal plain (Fig. 1) cored Lower Eocene (51 my) sea-floor basalt, suggesting a late Palaeocene-early Eocene period of sea-floor generation in the region. Well defined sea-floor spreading magnetic anomalies have yet to define the pattern of basin genesis. Falvey and Talwani (1969) however, have described linear magnetic anomalies of uncertain age correlation over the abyssal plain.

Previous syntheses of the tectonic development of the western Coral Sea such as that of Gardner (1970) are inadequate in the light of current age and stratigraphic control provided by the three DSDP sites in the region. The object of this paper is to use presently available well, seismic, and gravity data to formulate a speculative model for the development of the region consistent with plate tectonic concepts and currently accepted ideas on the development of continental margins as summarised by Falvey (1974) and Deighton et al. (1976).

STRATIGRAPHY

Seismic reflection data obtained during the Bureau of Mineral Resources (B.M.R.) Continental Margin Geophysical Survey (1970-1972) and tied to DSDP Site 209 establish a comprehensive picture of post-breakup sedimentation over the Queensland Plateau. Evidence of pre-breakup sedimentation is contained in the refraction and sonobuoy data of M. Ewing et al. (1970) and J. Ewing et al. (1970). Post-breakup depositional development of other plateaus in the region is established by correlation with events observed on the Queensland Plateau.

The time-stratigraphic section presented in Figure 2 and the corresponding structural section presented in Figure 3 are based on interpretation of all the available data, and are discussed fully in subsequent sections.

Queensland Plateau: post-breakup sedimentation

Seismic reflection profiles over the Queensland Plateau contain two unconformities (Fig. 4). The lower occurs at the

Fig. 3. Generalised structural cross-section corresponding to Figure 2. Seismic velocities are in km sec^{-1} and are taken from refraction data shown in Figure 1 (modified after Falvey and Taylor, 1974).

Fig. 4. Portions of BMR regional seismic lines from the Queensland Plateau. Line 14/34 passes approximately 65 km to the north of Lihou Reefs on the southeastern portion of the plateau while line 14/17 passes over the northwestern part of the plateau 150 km to the east-southeast of Osprey Reef.

Fig. 5. Thickness (in seconds of two way travel time) of Eocene sediment between the two unconformities is shown in Figures 2 and 4. To obtain actual thickness, note the velocities given in Figure 3. This compilation was made from the seismic data located in Figure 1 and the BMR regional survey (after Taylor, 1977).

base of the Tertiary sequence and marks the subsidence of the plateau following the commencement of spreading in the Coral Sea Basin. This unconformity appears as acoustic basement over much of the plateau and encompasses the breakup unconformity of Falvey (1974). DSDP Site 209 penetrated to within 50 m of this basement surface.

The upper unconformity occurs within the Tertiary-Recent section and correlates with the late Eocene-middle Oligocene unconformity cored at DSDP Site 209 (as well as Sites 210 and 287, see Fig. 2). Beneath this unconformity is a Lower to Middle Eocene section of seismic velocity 2.0-2.6 km.sec⁻¹. It is characterised by well stratified reflectors onlapping basement

highs. These reflectors are commonly disturbed by slight differential movement on basement faults or, more rarely, **abut faulted basement blocks**. Eocene reflectors usually bear a weak angular relationship to the overlying Oligocene-Recent reflectors (Fig. 4). On the outer edge of the plateau in water depths between 1500 m and 3500 m the Eocene section outcrops and is exposed over much of the outer plateau slope (Fig. 5).

The Eocene section is best developed away from the upper plateau surface where it often exceeds 1 km in thickness. However over most of the plateau this section is less than 500 m thick (Fig. 5). Areas of basement presently less than 1.5 km below sea level are completely devoid of Eocene sediments, yet support late Oligocene-Recent reef growth. This indicates that these regions were at sea level or subaerial during the early-middle Eocene.

The 300 m of Middle Eocene sediment cored at DSDP Site 209 contained an upward decreasing terrigenous component observed within 50 m of acoustic basement (breakup unconformity). The substantial variations in thickness of this layer (Fig. 5) broadly illustrate the pattern of onlap on to the subsiding plateau. It is important to note that not only does the depositional environment increase in water depth upwards through the Eocene, but that this trend continues monotonically into the section overlying the unconformity. This is also noted in the other DSDP sites 210 and 287 where absolute water depth is much greater (Fig. 1). Consequently the unconformity is considered to represent submarine erosion, which should also account for some of the variations in thickness noted in Figure 5.

The Upper Oligocene-Recent section consists of a basal winnowed foraminiferal sand, biogenic carbonate ooze (DSDP Site 209), reef detritus and coral reefs. The reefs grow directly on basement highs devoid of Eocene sediment cover. At distance from the coral reefs the Oligocene-Recent sequence is characterised by an undisturbed, acoustically transparent section of seismic velocity 1.8-2.0 km sec⁻¹. Nearer to reefs the section becomes increasingly stratified, and the velocity increases to 2.0-2.3 km sec⁻¹, similar to that of the underlying Eocene section. This is attributed to the presence of reef derived material in the section.

The post-breakup history of the plateau may be summarised as:

- (a) commencement of plateau subsidence in the early Eocene.
- (b) transgressive onlap of Eocene terrigenous and pelagic sediment onto subsiding basement.
- (c) restricted submarine erosion during the late Eocene-middle Oligocene.
- (d) establishment of coral reefs on subsiding basement highs in the late Oligocene-early Miocene with pelagic deposition prevailing on deeper areas of the plateau. This pattern has persisted until the present.

Post-breakup relationships are best illustrated in BMR seismic profile 14/48, which crosses the plateau to the south of Osprey Reef (Fig. 6). An extension of Osprey Reef was established on a basement high in the late Oligocene, immediately following the Eocene/Oligocene submarine erosional event. Subsequently a wedge of reef derived detritus was built out over the faulted Eocene sequence. With further plateau subsidence the reef extension died and pelagic carbonate deposition dominated the remainder of the sequence.

Queensland and Townsville Troughs

Tertiary sediments in excess of 1.5 km characterise the Queensland and Townsville Troughs (Fig. 1), both of which appear to be steeply faulted grabens. Both troughs exhibit the

Fig. 6. Interpretation of BMR regional seismic line 14/48 the western part of which passes 35 km to the south of Osprey Reef. The pinnacle is the dead southern extension of the Osprey Reef. The two unconformities are shown as well as the reef detrital apron and the Eocene outcrop (see Fig. 5 and text).

same velocity structure in the Tertiary sequence as observed on the Queensland Plateau, suggesting the presence of thick Eocene as well as late Oligocene to Recent sequences. Pinchin and Hudspeth (1975) have used sonobuoy data to map these sequences in the Queensland Trough.

Marion Plateau

Eocene reflectors rest unconformably on basement on the eastern slope of the Marion Plateau (Fig. 7, profile 13/58). The total absence of Eocene sediments on the plateau proper together with evidence of extensive past coral reef growth indicates that the plateau was above sea level throughout the Eocene and Oligocene, eventually subsiding below sea level in the late Oligocene-early Miocene.

Eastern and Papuan Plateaus

The unconformities noted on the Queensland Plateau are present on the Eastern (Fig. 7, profile 215) and Papuan Plateaus. Eocene sediment thickness ranges from zero to in excess of 1 km beneath the Moresby Canyon (Fig. 1) and parts of the Eastern Plateau. Eocene reflectors onlap on to basement highs and are commonly disturbed by faulting. To the north of the Eastern Plateau in the Moresby Trough the Tertiary sequence thickens rapidly and no Eocene/Oligocene unconformity can be recognised.

Coral reef growth is only present on a basement high at the northwest corner of the Eastern Plateau. The absence of reef growth on other basement highs with zero Eocene sediment cover suggests that these highs had subsided too far below sea level by the end of the submarine erosional event for reefs to be established, or that the highs were at substantial depth before the commencement of submarine erosion and that the Eocene section has been completely removed. The thin development of Eocene and the relationship of the unconformity to basement highs suggest that the latter is the case on the Papuan Plateau.

Louisiade Plateau

Scattered reflection profiles over the Louisiade Plateau indicate a similar pattern of development to that of the Queensland Plateau. The breakup unconformity is marked by a faulted basement and is overlain by up to 1 km of Tertiary sediment. A correlative of the Eocene/Oligocene unconformity is present over the plateau and defines an Eocene sequence averaging 250-300 m in thickness. Extinct or presently growing reefs are absent from the plateau and most basement highs have Eocene sediment cover implying that the plateau was completely submerged by the late Eocene.

Fig. 7. Portions of BMR regional seismic lines from the Marion Plateau (line 13/58 which approaches to within 8 km of Marion Reef in the west) and from the Eastern Plateau (line 215 which lies 40 km directly south of Eastern Fields Reef). Eocene sediments are absent from the Marion Plateau but occur beneath an upper unconformity on the plateau slope. A pronounced breakup unconformity is evident in the seismic line from the Eastern Plateau. The basement high is covered by a thin veneer of Eocene sediments which thicken over the basement depression to the east. Eocene reflectors are terminated by the submarine unconformity in the east of the section.

Pre-Breakup Sedimentation

Plateau basement velocities of 5.0-5.7 km sec⁻¹ are considered by M. Ewing et al. (1970) to represent Upper Palaeozoic sediments and metamorphics related to the onshore Tasman Geosyncline. Over much of the plateau the post-breakup section (1.8-2.6 km sec⁻¹) rests unconformably on such basement (Fig. 3).

In the Queensland and Townsville Troughs, the Queensland Plateau slope, and parts of the Queensland Plateau proper, the Tertiary sequence is, however, separated from the Palaeozoic basement by the development of up to 3 km of material with seismic velocity 2.8-4.5 km sec⁻¹. Where visible on reflection records on the plateau this section lies beneath the breakup unconformity and its disposition is suggestive of sediment infilling fault bounded basement depressions.

To the south of the region in the Capricorn Basin, Upper Cretaceous non-marine, terrigenous sediment (Ericson, 1976) cored in Capricorn-1A and Aquarius-1 has seismic velocities of 2.5-4.5 km sec⁻¹ (Australian Gulf Oil Company, 1968a, b; Fig. 8). The sediments are considered to represent alluvial fan deposits adjacent to fault scarps grading into marginal marine facies in the centre of the basin, and are separated from the overlying late Oligocene-Recent section by an unconformity (Ericson, 1976).

Correlation with the Capricorn Basin sequence, together with the clearly fault bounded nature of the deposits in the Queensland and Townsville Troughs therefore suggests that the 2.8-4.5 km sec⁻¹ material developed in the Queensland Plateau-Trough area (Fig. 3) represents a clastic rift valley sequence, developed in the late Cretaceous-Palaeocene prior to seafloor spreading in the Coral Sea. Gravity modelling, described in the Structure section below, supports this interpretation. The Halifax Basin at the southern end of the Queensland Trough (identified by Allen and Hogetoorn, 1970, using aeromagnetic data) probably contains a rift valley sequence in the lower part of that section.

STRUCTURE

Regional gravity field data, plus the seismic reflection and refraction data summarised in the previous section, provide valuable insight into crustal structure. Gravity maps of the western Coral Sea have been presented by Falvey and Talwani (1969), and Falvey (1972), and also discussed by Falvey and Taylor (1975). The most comprehensive gravity map to date is that by the Bureau of Mineral Resources (1976).

Falvey and Talwani (1969) noted the parallelism of gravity anomalies over the Queensland Trough and western Queensland Plateau with those of the onshore Palaeozoic

Fig. 8. Capricorn Basin structural cross-section (modified after Ericson, 1976). The seismic velocities obtained from Australian Gulf Oil Company (1968a, b) are in km sec^{-1} . Note the correlation with interpreted Queensland Plateau structure and velocities in Figure 3.

geosyncline, suggesting that the basement rocks are an integral part of the Tasman Geosyncline. Falvey and Taylor (1969) extended this interpretation by noting the coincidence of gravity lows with the development of 1-3 km of rift-related sediments (rift-valley sequence) over the Queensland and Townsville Troughs, and basin margins of the Queensland, Papuan and Eastern Plateaus.

Gravity Modelling

Figures 9 and 10 show computed two dimensional gravity models along two profiles extending northeastward from the Queensland continental shelf, over the Queensland Plateau and Coral Sea Abyssal Plain (Fig. 1). Observed gravity values and bathymetry were obtained from Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory and projected on to the two lines of section shown in Figure 1. Pre- and post-breakup structure was determined from the seismic reflection and refraction data summarised previously. Initially isostatic compensation across each section was assumed at a depth of 30 km relative to a standard isostatic column on the Queensland coast, consisting of a 30 km thick sea level section of 2.85 gm cm^{-3} , in accord with the crustal thickness determined from CRUMP data by Findlayson (1968). The mantle interface derived using the assumption of perfect compensation was later smoothed to derive a more realistic "moho" and the gravity recalculated. Regional isostatic balance is maintained and the resulting local differential load at any point across each section does not exceed $5 \times 10^4 \text{ gm cm}^{-2}$ and at most points is less than $2 \times 10^4 \text{ gm cm}^{-2}$.

Densities

The density assigned to the Tertiary-Recent sediments (seismic velocity $1.8-2.6 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$) is 2.0 gm cm^{-3} , and that to the proposed rift-valley sequence ($2.8-4.5 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$) 2.4 gm cm^{-3} . For simplicity the $5.0-5.7 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$ and the $6.0-6.8 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$

sec^{-1} main continental layers have not been differentiated and are ascribed a density of 2.85 gm cm^{-3} . Similarly oceanic layers 2 and 3 have a combined density of 2.95 gm cm^{-3} . These simplifications were tested and observed to make only a very minor difference to the theoretical gravity values. A deep crustal layer with a velocity of $7.0-7.6 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$ observed over the outer edge of the Queensland Plateau and beneath the Townsville Trough is assigned a density of 3.00 gm cm^{-3} . Because of the elapsed time since the cessation of spreading (45-50 m.y.) mantle is considered uniform beneath the plateau and basin with a density of 3.35 gm cm^{-3} .

Results

Two models are shown for each profile (Figs. 9 & 10). In one the deep crustal layer ($7.0-7.6 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$) is omitted, while in the other it is present beneath the plateau, plateau slope and trough. The latter is consistent with the hypothesis of Falvey (1974) that the $7.0-7.6 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$ layer developed beneath continental margins is a result of deep crustal metamorphism associated with high heat flow during the rifting stage of continental margin development. As such this deep metamorphic layer would be expected to reach maximum development in continental crust adjacent to the basin margin and beneath the troughs. These are locations where it was detected on seismic refraction lines (M. Ewing et al., 1970).

Given the previously defined standard isostatic column, both model profiles give theoretical values 15-20 mgals below the observed. This observation correlates closely with the value of the geoidal anomaly (Fig. 1) in the region (Kaula, 1972). Kaula (1972) and McQueen and Stacey (1976) have suggested the cause of geoidal variations is related to asthenospheric flow or variations in mantle phase boundaries. As such it lies below the lithosphere and below the depth of any accepted isostatic model and is consequently not taken into account in the determination of the theoretical gravity. The calculated gravity curves were adjusted by the average geoidal anomaly along their length; 15 mgals in the case of profile AA' and 20 mgals for BB'.

When the geoidal anomaly is taken into account a very close correspondence results between the calculated and observed gravity values. The deep crustal layer appears to have little gravity expression except possibly for the outer edge of the plateau on profile AA'. Here the slight upward slope in the observed gravity curve can best be approximated (within the constraints set by seismic data) by the presence of a rising deep crustal layer. Gravity values for the model without the deep metamorphic layer are 10-20 mgals below the observed at this location.

Rapid thinning of continental crust from 25 km to 11 km occurs beneath the outer edge of the plateau slope and upper rise. The thinning is more pronounced in the case of the models which include the deep crustal layer. If attenuation and thinning of the continental crust by stretching and "necking" or hot creep (Dewey & Bird, 1970; Bott, 1971; Artemjev & Artyushkov, 1971) were to be considered at all feasible, then it would appear to be strictly limited to a maximum of 40 km across the plateau rise on the basis of the isostatic restriction assumed in the models presented.

A feature of both profiles is the dependence of the shape of the gravity curves over the plateau on the upper 5-10 km of crustal structure. The distribution of rift-valley sediments shown in the profiles is necessary to achieve the form of the gravity curves. Lows in observed gravity show good correlation with the development of rift-valley sediments and/or greatly thickened Tertiary-Recent sediments. The only exception occurs on the basinward half of the plateau on AA' where the effect of the thickening rift-valley section is offset by the rising

Fig. 9. Computed two-dimensional gravity models for profile AA' located in Figure 1. The upper profile was modelled on the assumption that a crustal layer with velocity 7.0-7.6 km sec⁻¹ was not regionally significant, and the lower profile on the assumption that it was significant. Note the better fit of the lower profile over the outer plateau based on this latter assumption. An adjustment of +15 mgals has been made to the computed anomaly to account for the geoidal anomaly (Fig. 1).

Fig. 10. Computed two dimensional gravity models for profile BB' located in Figure 1. The upper profile was modelled on the assumption that a crustal layer with velocity $7.0-7.6 \text{ km sec}^{-1}$ was not regionally significant and the lower profile on the assumption that it was significant. Note that in this case gravity does not distinguish between these assumptions. The difference presumably lies in the distribution of Eocene (Fig. 5) and Upper Cretaceous rift valley sediments — and their compensation — profile AA' being the more sensitive. An adjustment of +20 mgals has been made to the computed anomaly to account for the geoidal anomaly (Fig. 1).

deep crustal layer and mantle associated with the continental edge.

The small portion of the eastern end of the Papuan Plateau/Louisiade Archipelago modelled in Section BB' (Fig. 10) shows a similar structure to that encountered over the slope of the Queensland Plateau. This is considered further evidence for the rifted nature of both the north and south margins of the Coral Sea Basin. The smaller crustal thickness encountered beneath the northern continental margin of the basin is probably in part a reflection of the originally thinner nature of the crust on the outer edge of the Australian continent prior to rifting and breakup.

The correlation between gravity lows and the development of rift valley section observed in the models further suggests that the Bligh Trough lying between the Eastern and Queensland Plateaus contains a thick rift-valley section developed on thinned continental crust, as it is marked by an extensive 40 mgals gravity low, extending from the Queensland Trough.

TECTONIC EVOLUTION

Previous Reconstructions

The pattern of seafloor spreading in the Coral Sea Basin has, at the time of writing, not been defined by magnetic anomalies, unlike the well defined pattern in the Southern Ocean (Weissel & Hayes, 1972; Deighton et al., 1976). Falvey and Talwani (1969) identified some linear trends in an obscure anomaly sequence subparallel to the Queensland Plateau and Papuan margins suggesting an ill-defined but proximal pole of relative opening for the basin. The various attempted reconstructions based on this suggested pattern (Gardner, 1970; Davies and Smith, 1971) fail on careful consideration of physiography and Papua-New Guinea geology. Further, no previous reconstructions have taken strict account of plate boundary dynamics in the regional setting, nor have they been carried out by computed finite rotation on a sphere.

Basis of the Reconstruction

We have attempted to overcome many of these difficulties with a computer-drawn reconstruction of pre-Eocene physiography and geology (Fig. 11) using the following observations and assumptions:

- (1) The oceanic lithosphere was restricted to the Coral Sea Basin, Cato Trough and deep water environs. The continental lithosphere boundary occurs at the base of the steep outer plateau slope — sometimes defined by a seismic basement ridge or scarp (Boeuf and Doust, 1975; Deighton et al., 1976). The troughs (with the exception of the Cato Trough) are considered to be subsided continental crust.
- (2) There is minimal pre-Eocene continental overlap upon removal of the oceanic lithosphere.
- (3) Subduction of Coral Sea Basin oceanic lithosphere has *not* occurred beneath the Papuan Plateau and slope — i.e. the entire basin is still preserved. This is clearly supported by seismic reflection data (J. Ewing et al., 1970; and DSDP leg 21, unpubl. profile) and free-air gravity anomalies (Falvey and Taylor, 1974; and B.M.R., 1976). Both margins of the basin, in fact, resemble normal rifted Atlantic margins (Fig. 10).
- (4) Consideration of the total dynamics of the inferred early Eocene plate boundary — divergent in the Coral Sea — should not violate pre-Eocene geology in Papua-New Guinea. We have permitted *no* relative motion between the Fly Platform and Australia (cf. Gardner, 1970).

There is no evidence for any plate boundary (relative motion) between the Eastern Plateau and the Fly Platform —

indeed the Cenozoic and Mesozoic integrity of this whole region supports our contention that there has been no seafloor spreading, say, in the Bligh Trough. This contention is further supported by the regional gravity pattern. The gravity expression of the Bligh Trough is that of thinned continental crust (previous section) trending north-south, terminating the west northwest trending gravity high associated with the oceanic Coral Sea Basin (Falvey & Taylor, 1974).

The geographic small circle traced by the Lagaip-Bismarck fault zones (Fig. 11) and the Moresby Trough is considered to represent the continuation of the basin spreading centre as a transform plate boundary. This boundary meets the Pacific-Australian plate boundary to the northwest in a trench-trench-fault triple junction. The best-fit reconstruction shown in Figure 11 was achieved by a clockwise finite rotation of Papua with respect to Australia about a pole at lat. 11.3°S, long. 141.3°E, by 14.5°. This finite rotation also moves the Louisiade Plateau to the eastern edge of the Queensland Plateau. With a lesser rotation angle it also closes the Cato Trough, which may also be of Paleocene-early Eocene age.

This reconstruction is also consistent with the concepts of Dow et al. (1972) and Bain et al. (1975) on the nature and significance of the Lagaip and Bismarck faults, both of which separate the stable Australian continent from the tectonically unstable New Guinea Mobile Belt. Dow et al. (1972) suspected strongly transcurent motion in the Lagaip and Bismarck fault zones and Bain et al. (1975) suggest major activity on the Bismarck fault in the early Tertiary.

Plate Dynamics

The dynamic implications of the above reconstruction are illustrated in Figure 12 along with the predicted environments (discussed below). Prior to the earliest Eocene, the simplest assumption would be that the Pacific Plate lay north and east of Papua-New Guinea. Isotopic dates on the Papuan Ultramafics suggest a Jurassic-early Cretaceous seafloor (Davies, 1971; Davies & Smith, 1971) which is consistent with the regional view of the Pacific at this time. Late Cretaceous *Globotruncana* in sediments associated with the basalts of the ultramafic belt are in a most uncertain relationship (Smith & Davies, 1976) and need not impose on the model the added complexity of a younger-than-Pacific plate in this position.

The convergence vectors of the Pacific relative to the Australian Plate in the vicinity of east Papua have been computed from poles given by Packham and Falvey (1976). The inferred nature of the plate boundary through the late Cretaceous and Palaeogene may thus be suggested:

- (1) 71-63 m.y. ago: The Pacific plate moved northwest relative to Australia at a rate of 4.3 cms yr⁻¹. The Pacific-Australian plate boundary was dominantly transform. No trench-arc systems (subduction) are suggested.
- (2) 63-53 m.y. ago: The relative motion was more westerly, though the boundary was still essentially transform. A very low rate of convergence, about 2 cm yr⁻¹, is manifest in east Papua and was probably a slow underthrust transform which contributed to the piling up and deformation of the sediments of the Owen Stanley Metamorphics.
- (3) 53-38 m.y. ago: Australia diverged from Antarctica changing the vector to convergence in a southwest direction. This motion would be compounded by spreading in the Coral Sea Basin. We envisage the onset of this convergence as being responsible for the obduction of the Papuan Ultramafic Belt.

The plate model outlined is satisfactorily constrained by what is known of the regional plate boundary geometry and dynamics.

Fig. 11. Proposed pre-Tertiary reconstruction of eastern and northern Papua New Guinea with respect to a fixed Australia (see text). The reconstruction is achieved by a computer rotation of -14.5° about a pole at lat. 11.3° S, long. 141.3° E. The continental edges with the Coral Sea Basin are represented by the lines drawn below 3000 m (see Figs. 3 and 13 to 15). The reconstruction of the Louisiade and Chesterfield Plateaus is only approximate, and does not affect later conclusions.

Palaeobathymetry

The method of estimating palaeobathymetry carried out by Deighton et al. (1976) remains contentious. However since that publication, support for mid-ocean ridge style (thermal cooling and contraction) subsidence applied to continental margins has been presented (Watts and Ryan, 1976 and pers. comm.; and Lynn, 1976). These authors support both the exponential

pattern and scaled amplitude proposed by Deighton et al. (1976), and it is that method we have applied to calculating bathymetric contours for the Coral Sea plateaus and margins in Figures 13 and 14. The extent of the initial elevation of the spreading ridge is however still controversial. We continue to support the concept of shallower ridge crests in young and narrow ocean basins. An alternative view is that the

aesthenosphere has an unalterable natural "head" at about 2600 m water depth. We contest that the thermal structure of the lithosphere is the same near just-parted continental lithosphere as beneath wider ocean basins (Lynn, 1976).

Palaeocurrents

The pattern of oceanic currents was quite different in the developing Coral Sea from that in the developing Southern Ocean. Scully-Power (1973) has shown that intermediate water and most shallow water enters the western Coral Sea from the east-northeast, gyres, and flows south — the Trade Wind Drift. Such a warm water circulation has almost certainly occurred throughout the Neogene, and probably the Oligocene as well. From the earliest Oligocene the basin was only 18° south of its present latitude and undoubtedly under subtropical influence, as evidenced by warm water nannofossils and foraminifera in DSDP Sites 209, 210 and 287 (Burns, Andrews et al., 1973; Andrews, Packham et al., 1975).

However through the Eocene history of the basin, circulation would have been quite different:

- (1) The basin would have been much shallower and the Louisiade and Chesterfield Plateaus either emergent or so shallow as to block any significant current flow from an easterly direction.
- (2) The already fully open Tasman Sea (Hayes and Ringis, 1973) would have provided a convenient path for northward flowing cool temperature water. Low volume, shallow and intermediate circulation through the Cato Trough would be dominant, as evidenced by cold water forams in DSDP Sites 209, 210 and 287 (ref. cit.).

This proposed change in oceanic current direction, volume and velocity is interpreted as being responsible for the Eocene-Oligocene unconformity observed in these DSDP sites. This unconformity has previously been attributed to the generation of Antarctic bottom water associated with global cooling prior to the final separation of Antarctica and Australia (Burns, Andrews et al., 1973; Andrews, Packham et al., 1975; Kennett et al., 1972; Kennett, Houtz et al., 1974).

There is considerable evidence against such an origin for the unconformity:

- (1) The first appearance of ice rafted detritus in the Ross Sea, Antarctica, is late Oligocene (Hayes, Frakes et al., 1975) and in Western Antarctica, early Miocene (Hollister, Craddock et al., 1974; Barker, Dalziel et al., 1974). The cooling phase marked by the appearance of this detritus culminated in the Pliocene (Hayes, Frakes et al., 1975).
- (2) Palynological evidence suggests a cool temperature Eocene climate in Antarctica while nannofossils suggest relatively warm waters bordering at least part of the Antarctic continent at this time (Kemp, 1975; Hayes, Frakes et al., 1975). This environmental pattern apparently persisted into the early Oligocene when rapid cooling commenced.
- (3) No Eocene/Oligocene unconformity is evident in DSDP Site 274 on the continental rise to the north of the Ross Sea. Rather a Miocene/Oligocene unconformity is present, related to the generation of Antarctic bottom water (Hayes, Frakes et al., 1975). This is significantly later (10 m.y.) than the onset of the unconformity in the Coral Sea.
- (4) Nannofossil assemblages in the Eocene sections of DSDP sites in the Coral Sea indicate a warming during the middle Eocene (Burns, Andrews et al., 1973) not the cooling expected with the development of a significant Antarctic bottom water flow into the region. This, coupled with the change of oceanic regime evidenced in the microfauna and flora, from temperate to subtropical

across the unconformity, suggests that a change to tropical or subtropical oceanic current regime is responsible for the unconformity.

- (5) The time span of the unconformity is 10 m.y. longer at Site 209 on the Queensland Plateau than Site 210 on the abyssal plain. This is inconsistent with an Antarctic bottom water origin for the feature.

With these points in mind it is considered more likely that a change in circulation pattern from northerly flowing cool temperate water to southerly flowing subtropical to tropical water is responsible for the unconformity.

Palaeoenvironments

The prediction of palaeoenvironments in the Coral Sea region is a far more speculative enterprise than that undertaken by Deighton et al. (ref. cit.) for the southern margin. Specific well control is extremely sparse, and so our environmental subdivisions somewhat less specific. On the legend common to Figures 2, 3, 8, 12, 13 and 14, we attempt to classify only a general non-marine facies and a marginal marine facies, including the rift valley section. Our use of the marine ingression symbol is purely hypothetical. Since reef detritus has been interpreted on seismic sections (Fig. 6), it is distinguished from true reefs and general carbonate shelf facies. Figures 13, 14 and 15 represent a best estimate based on the theory and hypotheses of preceding sections.

Palaeocene — Figure 12

During the pre-breakup rift valley stage horst-and-graben development was probably everywhere similar to that in the Capricorn Trough. A complex pattern of subsequently "failed rift arms" outlined future marginal plateaus. An infra-breakup stage in the later Palaeocene presumably involved axial subsidence, increasing marine influence and delineation of the incipient Lagaip-Bismarck Transform. The Pacific margin of the "Australian" continent was the site of deposition of clastics later to become the Owen Stanley Metamorphics. Gentle convergence along this largely transform plate boundary should have thickened this sediment pile.

The only known Danian sediment in the onshore region occurs in one small outcrop near Port Moresby (Palmieri, 1971), yet reworked Danian-Palaeocene material (*Globorotalia pseudobulloides*) is found in Lower Eocene sediments at the base of DSDP Site 287 directly above oceanic basement (Palmieri, 1971). This suggests that more extensive deposits of Danian-Palaeocene age exist on bordering submarine continental regions. It is considered evidence of an active infra-breakup stage.

Early Eocene — Figure 13

The probably short-lived active spreading event responsible for the basin had ended by this time. The essential structural style of the Papua-New Guinea Mobile Belt would have been established by its compressive interaction with the Pacific Plate. Limited subsidence of all surrounding plateaus would prevent other than cool temperate water inflow from the south for some time. Deposition was only gradually transgressive with strong development of clastic aprons around extensive highs on plateaus. This is typified by the mixed environment of the Lower Tertiary in the Capricorn Trough (Fig. 8).

Late Eocene — Figure 14

Northerly movement of the Australian Plate combined with deepening of the Louisiade Plateau would have permitted the tentative beginnings of Trade Wind Drift driven oceanic circulation. The Oligocene unconformity is probably related to

Fig. 12. Pre-Eocene palaeogeography showing the probable distribution of uppermost Cretaceous rift valleys. Fault scarps are diagrammatic and environments speculative except in the Capricorn Basin (Fig. 8). The palaeogeography is based on the reconstruction in Figure 11 with the present Papua New Guinea coastline omitted. The major plate boundary and the motion of the Pacific with respect to the Australian Plate for the Palaeocene is also shown. These convergent vectors for the Upper Cretaceous, Palaeocene and Eocene are also shown in the inset.

Fig. 13. Early Eocene depositional environments and palaeogeography at the cessation of seafloor spreading in the Western Coral Sea. The spreading ridge, transforms and continent-ocean boundaries are also shown. Coral reefs have been added for geographic reference only. Oceanic currents were probably weak and cool, coming from the south.

Fig. 14. Late Eocene depositional environments and palaeogeography at the onset of the submarine erosional event. The continent-ocean boundaries are shown. Coral reefs have been added for geographic reference only. Significant oceanic currents have just begun to enter the basin from the northeast.

this most significant current change — with a complex gyre causing submarine erosion similar to that which affected the Nautilus site in the Otway Basin (Deighton et al., 1976).

After further deepening of basin and plateaus through the Oligocene the catastrophic effects of this ocean current influx diminished, permitting the recognizable onset of true post-breakup conditions which extend to the present day.

General Conclusions

Two points stand out from this otherwise regional study as being of general importance:

- (1) It illustrates the application of a general predictive continental margin model with apparent success to an unknown area with very limited well control and limited seismic data.
- (2) The inter-relationship of local and regional subsidence, change of latitude, oceanic circulation changes and neobreakup deposition may be a general feature of continental margin development, *despite specific differences*. A possible unconformity terminating mixed neobreakup environments may be sensitive to the changes wrought by true oceanic conditions in the adjacent ocean basin. In this respect we note the similarity of the Coral Sea Oligocene, and Otway late Eocene unconformities with, for example, the Tithonian (145 m.y.) unconformity on the Northwest Shelf of Australia. The latter also occurs 10-15 m.y. after initiation of seafloor spreading (in this case in the Argo Abyssal plain at magnetic anomaly M-24 time). There is a simple relationship between the Tithonian unconformity and the actual breakup unconformity in the offshore Canning Basin. However these events have a most complex inter-relationship in the Beagle and Dampier Sub Basins (Powell, 1976).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A significant portion of this study represents Ph.D. research by Lloyd Taylor undertaken at the University of Sydney, under the supervision of Associate Professor Gordon Packham, whose advice and assistance are gratefully acknowledged. The raw gravity data were from a joint study by Falvey and Talwani (1969) and approved for use in this publication by Professor Manik Talwani of Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory. The section on tectonic evolution represents a joint project by the present authors. We wish to thank John Linde for his modifications to the two-dimensional gravity modelling programme, Len Hay for drafting the figures, and Margaret Falvey for critically reading the manuscript. The Director of the Bureau of Mineral Resources approved reprinting of the seismic sections.

Sincere thanks are also extended to Patrick Coleman who implanted the transform nature of the Mobile Belt in a disbelieving mind, and to Jeffrey Weissel for a valuable discussion of the recent surveys in the area.

REFERENCES

Allen, R. J., and D. J. Hogetoorn, 1970: Petroleum Resources of Queensland. Geol. Surv. Qld. Rept. 43.
 Andrews, J. E., G. H. Packham et al., 1975: Initial Reports of the Deep Sea Drilling Project, Volume 30. U.S. Govt. Printing Office, Washington.
 Artemjev, M. E., and E. V. Artyushkov, 1971: Structure and isostasy of the Baikal Rift and the mechanism of rifting. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 76, No. 5, pp. 1197-1211.
 Australian Gulf Oil Company, 1968(a): Well Completion Report—Gulf A.O.G. Capricorn No. 1A Well Completion Report: compiled by Carlsen, C. T., and T. C. Wilson (unpubl.).
 Australian Gulf Oil Company, 1968(b): Well Completion Report—Gulf A.O.G. Aquarius No. 1, compiled by Carlsen, C. T. and T. C. Wilson (unpubl.).

Bain, J. H. C., D. E. Mackenzie and R. J. Ryburn, 1975: Geology of the Kubor Anticline, Central Highlands of Papua New Guinea. *Bur. Miner. Resour. Aust. Bull.* 155.
 Barazangi, J., and J. Dorman, 1969: World seismicity maps compiled from ESSA, Coast & Geodetic Survey, epicenter data, 1961-1967. *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Amer.*, 59, pp. 369-380.
 Barker, P. F., I. W. D. Dalziel et al., 1974: Southwestern Atlantic leg 36, *Geotimes*, November 1974 pp. 16-18.
 Boeuf, M. G. and H. Doust, 1975: Structure and development of the southern margin of Australia. *APEA J.* 15, pp. 33-43.
 Bott, M. H. P., 1971: Evolution of young continental margins and formation of shelf basins. *Tectonophysics*, 11, pp. 319-327.
 Bureau of Mineral Resources, 1976: Preliminary Gravity Map of Melanesia.
 Burns, R. E., J. E. Andrews et al., 1973: Initial Reports of the Deep Sea Drilling Project, Volume 21. U.S. Govt. Printing Office, Washington.
 Davies, H. L., 1971: Peridotite-gabbro-basalt complex in Eastern Papua: an overthrust plate of oceanic mantle and crust. *Bur. Miner. Resour. Aust. Bull.* 128.
 Davies, H. L., and I. E. Smith, 1971: Geology of Eastern Papua. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.*, 82, pp. 3299-3312.
 Deighton, I., D. A. Falvey and D. J. Taylor, 1976: Depositional environments and geotectonic framework: Southern Australian continental margin. *APEA J.* 16, pp. 25-26.
 Dewey, J. F., and J. M. Bird, 1970: Mountain belts and the new global tectonics. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 75, Pt. 14, pp. 2625-2647.
 Dow, D. B., J. A. J. Smit, J. H. C. Bain and R. J. Ryburn, 1972: Geology of the south Sepik Region, New Guinea. *Bur. Miner. Resour. Aust. Bull.* 133.
 Ericson, E. K., 1976: Capricorn Basin; in Knight, C. L. (Ed.), Economic Geology of Australia & Papua New Guinea 3. Petroleum, pp. 464-473.
 Ewing, J. I., R. E. Houtz, and W. J. Ludwig, 1970: Sediment distribution in the Coral Sea. *J. Geophys. Res.* 75, No. 11, pp. 1963-1972.
 Ewing, M., L. V. Hawkins and W. J. Ludwig, 1970: Crustal Structure of the Coral Sea. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 75, No. 11, pp. 1953-1962.
 Falvey, D. A., 1972: The nature and origin of marginal plateaux and adjacent ocean basins off northern Australia. Ph.D. thesis, University of N.S.W. (unpubl.).
 Falvey, D. A., 1974: The development of continental margins in plate tectonic theory. *APEA J.* 14, pp. 95-106.
 Falvey, D. A., and M. Talwani, 1969: Gravity map and tectonic fabric of the Coral Sea. (abs.) *Geol. Soc. Am. Ann. Mtg.* Nov. 1969, Abs. 7.
 Falvey, D. A. and L. W. H. Taylor, 1974: Queensland Plateau and Coral Sea Basin: structural and time stratigraphic patterns. *Bull. Aust. Soc. Explor. Geophys.* 5, No. 4, pp. 123-126.
 Finlayson, D. M., 1968: First arrival data from the Carpentaria Region Upper Mantle Project. *J. Geol. Soc. Aust.*, 15, No. 1, pp. 33-50.
 Gardner, J. F., 1970: Submarine geology of the western Coral Sea. *Geol. Soc. Amer. Bull.* 81, pp. 2599-2614.
 Halunen, A. J., and R. P. Von Herzen, 1973: Heat flow in the western equatorial Pacific Ocean. *J. Geophys. Res.* 78, No. 23, pp. 5195-5208.
 Hayes, D. E., L. A. Frakes et al., 1975: Initial Reports of the Deep Sea Drilling Project, Volume 28. U.S. Govt. Printing Office, Washington.
 Hayes, D. E. and J. Ringis, 1973: Seafloor spreading in the Tasman Sea. *Nature*, 243, pp. 454-458.
 Hollister, C. D., C. Craddock et al., 1974: Deep sea drilling in the southeast Pacific Basin. *Geotimes*, August 1974 pp. 16-19.
 Karig, D. E., 1971: Origin and development of marginal basins of the western Pacific. *J. Geophys. Res.* 76, No. 11, pp. 2542-2561.
 Kaula, W. M., 1972: Global gravity and mantle convection. *Tectonophysics*, 13, pp. 341-359.
 Kennett, J. P., et al., 1972: Australian-Antarctic continental drift, palaeocirculation changes and Oligocene deep sea erosion. *Nature Phys. Sci.* 239, No. 91, pp. 51-55.
 Kennett, J. P., R. E. Houtz et al., 1974: Initial Reports of the Deep Sea Drilling Project, Volume 29. U.S. Govt. Printing Office, Washington.
 Kemp, E. M., 1975: Palynology of Leg 28 Drill Sites, Deep Sea Drilling Project; in Hayes, D. E., L. A. Frakes et al. (Ed.), Initial Reports of the Deep Sea Drilling Project, V. 28, pp. 599-608. U.S. Govt. Printing Office, Washington.

- Lynn, M. P., 1976: Correlation between well logs, depositional environments and subsidence in the Gippsland and Otway Basins post breakup. Unpub. B.Sc.(Hons.) thesis, University of Sydney (unpubl.).
- Macdonald, K. C., B. P. Luyendyk and R. P. Von Herzen, 1973: Heat flow and plate boundaries in Melanesia. *J. Geophys. Res.* 78, No. 14, pp. 2537-2546.
- McQueen, H. W. S., and F. D. Stacey, 1976: Interpretation of low degree components of gravitational potential in terms of undulations in mantle phase boundaries. *Tectonophysics*, 34, T1-T8.
- Packham, G. H. and D. A. Falvey, 1976: Palaeogene Pacific-India Plate Interaction. *25th Inter. Geol. Cong. Abs.*, 3, p. 876. Paper in press in symposium volume, ed. S. Uyeda.
- Palmieri, V., 1971: Occurrence of Danian at Port Moresby. *Qld. Geol. Surv. Rept.* 63.
- Pinchin, J. and J. W. Hudspeth, 1975. The Queensland Trough: its petroleum potential based on some recent geophysical results. *APEA J.* 15, pp. 21-31.
- Powell, D. E., 1976: The geological evolution of the continental margin off northwest Australia. *APEA J.* 16, pp. 13-23.
- Sclater, J. G., 1972: Heat flow and marginal basins of the western Pacific. *J. Geophys. Res.* 77, No. 29, pp. 5705-5719.
- Sclater, J. G. and U. G. Ritter, 1972: Heat flow in the southwestern Pacific. *J. Geophys. Res.* 77, No. 29, pp. 5697-5704.
- Scully-Power, P. D., 1973. Oceanography of the Coral Sea: the winter regime, in Fraser, R. (Ed.), *Oceanography of the South Pacific*, pp. 129-133. *N.Z. Nat. Comm. for UNESCO*, Wellington.
- Smith, I. E. and H. L. Davies, 1976: Geology of the Southeast Papuan mainland. *Bur. Miner. Resour. Aust. Bull.* 165.
- Taylor, L. W. H., 1977. The western Coral Sea: sedimentation and tectonics. Ph.D. thesis, the University of Sydney (unpubl.).
- Watts, A. B. and W. B. F. Ryan, 1976. Flexure of the lithosphere and continental margin basins. *Tectonophysics*, 36, No. 1-3, pp. 25-44.
- Weissel, J. K. and D. E. Hayes, 1972. Magnetic anomalies in the southeast Indian Ocean; in Hayes, D. E. (Ed.). *Antarctic Oceanology 11: The Australian-New Zealand Sector. Antarctic Res. Ser.* 19, pp. 165-196.